

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

University of Bahrain

Collage of Arts

Department of English Language and Literature

ENGL450 (Project writing)

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

Submitted by: Fatima Hassan Abbas Nowaiser

ID Number: 20193504

Supervised by: Dr. Priya Sharma

Section: 1

Date of Submission: 16 May 2024

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

Abstract:

Momo by Michael Ende and 1984 by George Orwell are both excellent social fiction novels that discuss major social concerns. This research aims to inspect the two novels to find differences and correlations between them. This research will delve into the social themes presented in Momo and 1984 to find what ties those themes together as well as what makes Momo and 1984 social fiction novels. Moreover, this research will consider the possibility of the novels being Dystopian/Utopian novels. Lastly, it will mention the differences between them. This research is conducted on data collected in a qualitative method by reading both novels and looking into past researches on them, and will be analyzed using a thematic approach.

Key terms: *Totalitarianism, Time, Society, Utopia, Dystopia, Power, Control.*

Table of Contents

Abstract:	2
1 Introduction	5
1.1 Background of the Problem	5
1.2 Statement of the Problem	5
1.3 Purpose of Research	6
1.4 Research questions	6
1.5 The significance of the study	6
1.6 Research Methods and procedures	6
1.6.1 Methods of Data collection	6
1.6.2 Data collection procedures	6
2 Literature review	7
2.1 Theoretical Background	7
2.1.1 1984's Major Themes	7
2.1.2 Momo's Major Themes	7
2.2 Previous researches	8
2.2.1 First research	8
2.2.2 Second research	8
2.2.3 Third research	9
2.2.4 Fourth research	10
2.2.5 Fifth research	10
2.2.6 Sixth research	11
2.3 Theoretical Framework	12
3 Methodology	13
4 Findings	13
5 Discussion	14
5.1 1st question:	14
Time as a mean of Control	14
Language as a mean of control	14
5.2 2nd question:	15
1984 as a Dystopian and Momo as a Utopian social fictions	15
5.3 3rd question:	16

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

Capitalism.....	16
Audience and Tone.....	17
6 Conclusion	18
7 Limitations.....	18
8 References.....	19

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

1 Introduction

1.1 Background of the Problem

Momo by Michael Ende is considered a children novel, on the other hand, 1984 by George Orwell is considered a young adult – adults' book, both are social novels that discuss important social issues. Momo tells the story of a young girl with an unknown background, that appears suddenly in a city and starts living at the amphitheater with the help of the families living there. Momo is fond of the people as much as they are fond of her and all is going well until one day, the men in gray spread in the city like wildfire, stealing people's time and therefore joy. Momo fights the men in gray and saves her friends and things are good again. Momo discuss social issues like management or commodification of time, and abuse of power. As for 1984, it tells the story of Winston who lives in Oceania, a city that is controlled by the Party and its leader Big Brother. Winston works in the Records Department of the Ministry of Truth; he changes documents and events to support the Party's ideologies and fit their propaganda. Winston dislikes the Party and starts writing his thoughts in a diary and begins a forbidden relationship with Julia who is secretly against the Party too. Winston and Julia date secretly by the help of O'Brien, an inner Party member who Winston believes to be secretly trying to overthrow the Party with a group called the Brotherhood, He turns out to be a Thought police and gets both Winston and Julia to submit to the Party by torturing them. Social issues like Totalitarianism, propaganda, and surveillance are presented in 1984.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Social fiction is a genre that contains many sub-genres but is essentially there to criticize different social issues to deliver a warning or an insight to the reader. Both Momo and 1984 are social fiction novels that discuss many societal issues in different ways and speaks to different audience. The novels have many similarities and differences in themes.

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

1.3 Purpose of Research

The purpose of this research is to explore the themes in both Momo and 1984 and recognize the similarities between them as social novels while looking into the Dystopias/Utopias sub-genre in relation to both novels.

1.4 Research questions

- 1- What social themes do the novels discuss and what is the relation between them?
- 2- What makes Momo and 1984 social fiction novels and are they considered Utopias/Dystopias?
- 3- What dissimilarities do these novels have?

1.5 The significance of the study

This research is done in order to notice the subtle connection between the novels when analyzed in depth. Moreover, it may help the reader notice the close relation that some sub-genres have.

1.6 Research Methods and procedures

1.6.1 Methods of Data collection

This research uses qualitative methods, data will be collected by reading both novels closely and reading secondary sources such as researches and scholarly articles. Textual analysis method and observational method will be used.

1.6.2 Data collection procedures

The data was analyzed using a thematic approach, major themes of both novels were identified and then studied to find links.

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

2 Literature review

2.1 Theoretical Background

2.1.1 1984's Major Themes

1984 by George Orwell explores totalitarianism through a parallel London, in the future called Oceania, ruled by a totalitarian regime called the Party. People of Oceania are watched by telescreens everywhere, the whole city is under surveillance thus privacy is nonexistent. The city is divided into three social classes, inner Party, outer party and the proles. Inner Party are privileged with more money, luxury, and privacy. Winston is a member of the outer Party; his job is to change past records. In Oceania, romantic relationships are prohibited and family relations are tense because even children will tell on their parents if they dare to oppose the Party which strips the individual from their human feelings. The Party works on eliminating the individual and going about everything with totality. Oceania has secret police called "Thought Police" and they are in charge of surveillance, Thought Police monitor and watch everyone in the city in order to keep them in check in case they commit "Thoughtcrime" since it is a crime to think badly of the Party, and if someone does, the "Thought Police" punishes them by mental and physical torture.

2.1.2 Momo's Major Themes

Momo by Michael Ende is a children's fantasy novel. The novel builds a nice world where people love, help, and give time to each other and Momo, who has a great ability to listen is a big help to those around her since her ability is substantial. However, that world is quickly shattered when enters the men in gray who steal people's time. Time is a major theme in the novel, when people around Momo start saving time, they strangely seem to have even less time. They leave their children with new invented games to compensate for their absence but their children feel neglected and the new games take away their imagination. Adults spend money on trivial things to get rid of their children and to feel the life of luxury which is a clear reference to consumerism, one of the gray men tries to manipulate Momo with a speaking doll and her shiny

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

things telling her that they will provide her with many things to play with and that things to wish for are endless. The men in gray are experts in manipulation, they study and watch people then convince them to save their time in the time-saving bank telling them slogans such as “Time is Money – Save it” (Ende, 1973, Chapter 6) and then stealing it to stay alive. The men in gray are able to control everyone around Momo even her closest friends end up as time savers. Momo is able to destroy and ruin the men in gray’s plans by the help of Master Hora (keeper of Time) and Cassiopeia (a turtle that can see half an hour into the future).

2.2 Previous researches

2.2.1 First research

“George Orwell and the theory of Totalitarianism: A 1984 retrospective” by George M. Enteen (1984) discusses the overlooked concepts of 1984 such as “Newspeak,” “Memory hole,” “Unperson,” and “Doublethink”. It is believed that Orwell have written 1984 with the thought of both Nazi Germany and Stalinist Russia. In 1984, Julia represents each and every citizen that hates the Party but can’t express it knowing that it will lead to their death, similarly in the Soviet Union where there is a lack of freedom in speech as an individual could never express what they feel about their own society. The control of the past is also apparent in Russia and other Soviet nationalities just like the concept of “Memory Hole” and “Unperson” in 1984 which suggests the deletion and the alteration of some figures and events of the past as a way for the Party to gain more power over the population. Orwell knows the power of language, which is why “Newspeak” was a centric element in 1984 and was both the beginning and the end of it, Orwell thinks that the reduction of words and meanings is the mechanism of linguistic degradation. Another way to control people is to make them stop thinking and just like Stalin tried to make Russians do, Big Brother’s “Doublethink” was a way to make people go blindly after anything the Party says without a single thought, Enteen mentions a statement made by Trotsky (1924) “...I know that one cannot be right against the party. One can be right only with the party and through the party, for history has not created any other path for the realization of what is right” which further prove his point about the idea of freezing the brains of the population.

2.2.2 Second research

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

“Orwell in 1984” by Jhon Atkins (1984) discusses Orwell’s possible stance if he was alive in the year 1984, taking into consideration his writings and views. Orwell has made a symbol of totalitarianism out of 1984 while he stood with democratic socialism, Totalitarianism is a combination of communism and fascism as understood of Orwell’s 1984. Orwell’s attraction to socialism is a result of his feelings towards injustice, traditional socialism that is based on equality, democracy, liberty and morality was what Orwell originally supported. If Orwell was alive, he would be willing to know the true motives behind the social democratic party that emerged in Britain. For him, communism and fascism are a distorted version of socialism, and both follow a totalitarian system. Orwell expressed several times how important it is to use clear and simple language in public discourse. Atkins covered Orwell’s views on socialism and totalitarianism, and explained how Orwell is concerned with the misuse of terms like socialism and fascism which brings back the simple language discourse. With quite a pessimistic view Orwell critiques the modern life that is based on consumerism, materialism and relies heavily on technology and on the other hand lacks warmth and sympathy as he praises the normal working classes for maintaining those human qualities.

2.2.3 Third research

“Nineteen eighty-four’s Dystopian vision: power and the individual” by Roar Hole (2007) discusses the society of 1984 explained by Louis Althusser’s Ideological States Apparatuses (ISA) and Repressive States Apparatuses (RSA) concepts. He explains how totalitarian regimes try to eliminate the individual and goes by totality in everything but the truth is, it works for the benefit of the Party only. As mentioned in (The Oxford Dictionary of Philosophy,” 2008) about Totalitarian state’s characteristics “all institutional and private arrangements are subject to control by the state.” The Totalitarian government dominates by using different mechanisms such as war, intense surveillance, and the elimination of the individual. “The war is a powerful instrument in ensuring the loss of individuality. War is a device to ensure unity and orthodoxy, and by making war literally continuous, the Party has created a device to maintain and facilitate their regime.” (Hole, 2007, page 1). Not only that but it also aims at continuous reproduction and continuous demand “The people are homogenized by the perpetual shortage of products, which forces a society of equality of the lowest terms.” (Hole, 2007, page 16). Althusser divides society into ideological (ISA) and the state (RSA). The (ISA) is the ideologies and ideas that are

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

fed to the crowd by the state in order to control and manipulate it. In 1984 every institution works to support the same notions in order to brainwash the population and control it in different ways such as illustrating propagandas on the telescreens or destroying documents of the past, while (RSA) is the sensible version of the (ISA) where the Party actually practices sovereignty over the people of Oceania.

2.2.4 Fourth research

“Momo, Dogen, and the Commodification of Time” by Linda Goodhew and David Loy (2002) Compares the concept of time commodification in Momo to the Japanese Buddhist priest Dogen’s realization of time. First, it speaks of how people are experiencing the feeling of having less time lately and therefore more stress more work and less sleep. In a survey done in 1992 by the U.S. National Recreation and Park Association the results shows that 38 percent of Americans are feeling rushed. This is due to the commodification of time; the research gives a summary of Momo explaining how the men in gray fooled people to spend less time with their families and friends or having fun in order to save time since “Time is precious – Don’t waste it!” (Ende, 1973, Chapter 6). In the novel, Ende shows how Guido (Momo’s friend) loses direct connection to time once he started saving it (making his secretaries manage his time for him), how clock is what makes time commodifiable by reducing time to a number. On the other hand, Dogen thinks that objects are time and vice versa and that time is being itself therefore you should not separate them from each other. The writers conclude that today’s issue comes from the dualism between an event and its time and people always feeling the need to do something with their time but the more people objectify time the more they detach from it, which brings back to the Buddhist’s realization that you are time thus you should always be one with time to not feel stressed and rushed. The solution for this is to stop commodifying time and feeling that you have to get something out of it but rather sacralize time itself. The research also mentions briefly how Ende exposes consumerism plans of dividing families and obstructing imagination.

2.2.5 Fifth research

“The Economic Thought of George Orwell” by Jennifer Roback (1985) is about Orwell’s views on economic. Roback claims that in order to understand Orwell’s dystopian vision and experience the thrill of it, you must be able to understand his economic views first. For Orwell,

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

both socialism and capitalism don't work and has many weaknesses. Orwell believed that socialism would lead to totalitarianism and that capitalism would lead to poverty. Orwell was a socialist with a Marxist economic view. As for technology, Orwell was neither with or against it but was more concerned with who would control it and what will it be used for. One of the reasons that made Orwell a socialist is the income inequality in a capitalism system. Capitalism has a deep connection with consumerism and it leads to overproduction of goods that can't be afforded by workers nor consumed by capitalists and this eventually causes an economic disaster. Orwell in general was not in a position to speak of economics as he lacked the knowledge and understanding of the price system and his views of both capitalism and socialism were based on his era.

2.2.6 Sixth research

“Momo, a ragged little girl, shows the way to Utopia: A study of listening, imagining, and taking time in a recent German novel” by Robert N. Peck (1991) explains how Momo is a novel that presents the uttermost essential and necessary characteristics for humans to reach Utopia which are listening, imagining, and taking time. The novel draws a Utopian vision especially after Momo defeats the men in gray and people are back to a beautiful harmonious life. Robert describes how Momo's ability to listen aspires people to open up, listen to each other and realize a lot about themselves and others, which leads them to reflect on themselves and change for the better as well as know theirs and others worth, this quality could contribute to an improved society where communication is smoother and empathy is felt. Similarly, imagining can be the key to realize problems, understand, and solve them. Imagination is necessary for new creations, a tool to see into things and beyond them therefore people can create their utopia and avoid bad decisions to move and evolve with modest consumption, furthermore, a life with imagining means a life where boredom do not exist. Momo and her friends never experience boredom because they have fun playing different games that they create and imagine. The third trait is taking time which is incarnated in the tortoise Cassiopeia, although the tortoise can see half an hour into the future, it is well aware that it can't see more than that therefore it takes its time to think through each step rather than rushing into it. This trait would lead to a better life because being careful and thinking about consequences would lead to less damage, humans tend to rush things such as promoting or using new products which costs them a lot and results in permeant

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

damages, Cassiopeia teaches a valuable lesson about taking time. Taking time is also important for human relationships, taking time to spend a few hours with your family or friends makes relationships stronger, as the men in gray plays mind tricks on people, they made sure to get them to spend less and less time together so they lose their human feelings and focus on material, their ways resemble the way rich exploits the poor. Taking time make people happy by being at ease and less stressed. The most important key for reaching Utopia is all of these traits working together in sync since they all affect each other. People are responsible for making this happen and everything depends on their will to do so.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

In 1984, the Party controls the past in order to control both the present and future and they also use the power of language to grow ideologies in people's brains in order to eliminate individuality to achieve true power while also keeping people in a constant need by keeping the state in war. Orwell hates the modern life with its consumerism and materialism he also believes that capitalism is bad for the income inequality and that people are losing human qualities like warmth and sympathy. In Momo, commodification of time leads people to feel rushed and to lose direct connection to time and to feel the need to get something out of every second which drives them away from themselves and people around them. Characteristics found in Momo (listening- imagining- taking time) are the way to achieve Utopia when working in unison. This research will find connections between themes and answer the research questions by combining results of previous researches mentioned in the literature review, other sources and researches, and the student's reading, analysis and observation of both novels.

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

3 Methodology

The research paper employed qualitative methodologies. The focus of this research is to compare the novels Momo and 1984 as social novels and to breakdown the social themes discussed in them to find similarities and differences, through a close text analysis of both novels and content analysis such as articles, blogs, and YouTube videos while also looking through and observing secondary data such as previous researches and readers reviews of both novels.

The data will be collected by using text and content analysis method, secondary data review, and observational method. The data will be analyzed using a thematic approach by finding patterns and analyzing themes moreover, a comparative approach will be used to identify similarities and dissimilarities between the novels and finally genre analysis will be applied on a small part to compare characteristics of both novels to those of certain genres.

4 Findings

Time as a mean of control: Villains in both novels use time in unique ways to control people and have power over them.

Language as a mean of control: In both novels, language holds a great power in controlling people. New language, slogans, and spoken ideologies make it easier for parties to control people.

1984 as a Dystopian and Momo as a Utopian social fictions: The novels discuss a number of social issues by portraying consequences of standing with or fighting against it. 1984 is a well-known dystopian novel with multiple dystopian characteristics meanwhile Momo is not considered a utopian novel although it has the key elements to reaching utopia.

Capitalism: In 1984, capitalism is announced a failure by the Party. In Momo, why and what makes capitalism a failure is portrayed to the reader in a creative way.

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

Audience and tone: The tones and closure in both novels are very different due to the different target audience of the authors.

5 Discussion

5.1 1st question:

Time as a mean of Control

In Momo (1973) by Michael Ende the main and most obvious theme is time, people want to save time, the gray gentlemen steal time, and Momo wants to save people's time. Time is an instrument to gain control over everyone, after manipulating people to save their time in the time-saving bank the gray gentlemen use it for their own survival while people on the other hand always feel rushed and have no time, that way it is easier to control and manipulate them into saving more time. In 1984 (1949) by George Orwell totalitarianism is the main theme that Orwell is fighting against in fear of a future ruled by it. Totalitarianism is an autocracy that is all about power and control over every aspect of people's lives using many means and ways. One of the major means to gain power and control is time, to control the present and the future, the Party controls the past and erase records and even people, as mentioned in the novel itself "Who controls the past controls the future" (Orwell, 1949, Chapter 3) Winston who works in the Records department of the Ministry of Truth was well aware of the Party's propaganda, he knew that other than him there was a few that remembered the real events of the past although the human's memory could fail them and make up non-existent memories when given a ground. Winston was afraid that the next generation would be unaware of the Party's games and will be the easiest to manipulate and control therefore will be loyal to the Party.

Language as a mean of Control

Oceania has found a new language "Newspeak" as the official language for the state, in hope to replace Old speak (standard English) by 2050. The main purpose of the said language is to "diminish the range of thought." (Orwell, 1949, Chapter 5), by eliminating words and replacing some which narrows the range of thoughts. Newspeak has a direct connection to "Doublethink" which is believing in two opposite things and accepting both to be true. The party spreads many

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

slogans with contradictory things as equivalents such as “War is peace. Freedom is slavery. Ignorance is strength” (Orwell, 1949, Chapter 1) and the population is expected to believe in every single one of them without questioning or doubt. O’Brien, the inner Party member, describes how doublethink works as, although knowing that something is not true you make yourself forget that it is not true therefore you eventually believe it to be true. Like this, Newspeak and Doublethink work together as a tool for the Party to have complete control over the people of Oceania. In Oceania, the ministries names are the opposite of what they actually are for example, the ministry of truth provides lies and fabrication and the ministry of peace is in charge of genocidal wars and the ministry of love is all about sowing fear and dread in the population with its Thought police which tortures and manipulate anyone that tries to oppose the Party. finally, the ministry of plenty which is considered the country’s ministry of economy, unlike what the name implies, people of Oceania are living in poverty with no means of production, just like that Oceania’s ministries are the embodiment of Doublethink. Both Newspeak and Doublethink work together as a tool for the Party to control the minds of the population. In Momo, the men in gray use language to convince and manipulate people into saving their time with slogans like “Time is precious – Don’t waste it” and “Time is money – Save it” (Ende, 1973, Chapter 6). Those slogans are plastered all over the city in big screens so everyone could see them and become a time saver, by a short time, most of the adults were manipulated and time savers already. Momo and her friends fight the men in gray back by using language too, they demonstrate in the streets holding big signboards that has slogans to warn people of the gray men’s evil plans not only that but also singing a twenty-eight-verse song written by Guido especially for the demonstration with quiet a warning tone “Listen, folk, ere it’s too late, or you’ll live to rue your fate” (Ende, 1973, Chapter 8).

5.2 2nd question:

1984 as a Dystopian and Momo as a Utopian social fictions

Momo and 1984 are both social fiction novels because they discuss social issues and criticize them, they also call for reflection and taking action to solve and control those issues before they escalate to the point of no return. In Momo, there is a clear message to fight those who want to

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

steal your time and take you away from yourself and your people and in 1984 Orwell is warning people of the dictatorship regimes that wipe out the identity of the individual and controls every aspect of peoples' lives. 1984 is known as one of the most popular Dystopian novels with a terrifying image of a dystopian society "the picture of society in Nineteen Eighty-Four has an awful plausibility which is not present in other modern projections of our future." (Symons, 1949, page 247) the power held by the Party through bureaucratic ministries emphasizes the totalitarian regime of Oceania, the constant feel of being watched gives the novel the necessary features to be considered Dystopian. Technology plays a significant part in Dystopian societies, in 1984 the telescreen is the tool for surveillance and the teacher of Oceania that any ideology the Party wants to seed in people's mind is displayed through. Surveillance is a common theme in Dystopian literature, people in Oceania are under surveillance all the time which makes them cautious of every move and expression they make. The party in 1984 works on eliminating the individual and dehumanizing the people by distorting human feelings and taking away every meaningful thing to them. In Momo, the pleasant peaceful life before and after the appearance of the men in gray is the closest thing a utopia can be in the real world, although happiness can't be endless, people could never be equal or be treated equally, the life in Momo's city without the disturbance of the gray gentlemen is full of laughter and love and most importantly time. As previously mentioned, Robert N. Peck (1991) writes about the key elements to reach utopia that are found in Momo by Ende. Those elements are listening, taking time, and imagining, although Momo was not written as a utopian fiction and lacked characterizations of a utopian novel, it could be considered the process to create a real utopia that is not impossible to reach. However, Momo is not a utopian novel and the author did not write it to be one.

5.3 3rd question:

Capitalism

Despite both novels considering capitalism a negative system, the approach is completely different. In 1984, the Party announces capitalism as a failure already with no need to dive into how and why, on the other hand, the novel Momo as a whole is an allegory of a world that turns capitalist to show and make the reader feel what it would be like and realize how bad of a system capitalism is. Momo displays the main characteristics of capitalism, first is measurement and

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

commodification of time, for instance, one of the gray men calculates Figaro's time subtracting, dividing, adding and multiplying it as if it was a commodity, after that, he starts to persuade Figaro to save his money in the time-saving bank even giving him an interest rate by doubling the saved time if not withdrew for five years. Second, rush is essential in a capitalist world and Momo shows exactly how time-savers are always in a rush doing work and daily tasks that even their walk is more of a jog. Rush could also indicate lack of time which almost every adult in Momo is experiencing since they started saving time, they didn't have time to spend with their children nor their friends. Moreover, the men in gray are the embodiment of capitalism with their gray suits, fancy cars, and briefcases, they give interest rates, look lifeless, and get competitive with each other. The men in gray also hate slowing down, when Momo starts interfering with their plan therefore making adults slow down, the men in gray are in distress and they hurry to stop her, they have a meeting to share ideas on how they can stop Momo from slowing adults down. In the novel, Momo and her friends are fighting this system which is a clear sign that the author is also against it since children are supposed to be the ones ruled by nature rather than corrupted systems and societal concepts.

Audience and Tone

Since 1984 is considered an adult novel, it tackles issues on a realistic manner excluding the futuristic vision which is a must in science fiction novels. Momo, as a fantasy novel that has children as a target audience, is less realistic with supernatural and magical characters such as the men in gray, Cassiopeia, and even Momo who Iva M. Simurđić (2020) argued to be a "divine child". Considering the target audience, Momo has a dreamy, almost hopeful tone which is there for most of the novel excluding chapter 6, 7, and 9. It also has an innocent tone given that Momo, who is a child, is the heroine and her friends who are mostly children are very important to the story and overall, a somewhat a Utopian tone. On the other hand, 1984 has a very dull, gloomy, tragic, and pessimistic tone exactly that of a Dystopia. Despite both serving as a warning of cruel exploited systems, they end on different notes. 1984 ends disastrously with the undesirable vision happening and Winston losing himself completely to Big Brother meanwhile, Momo ends by defeating the evil men in gray and everything is better than ever. Momo provides solutions with a happy ending.

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

6 Conclusion

The novels have many shared themes as mentioned above. Both are good written social fiction novels with good messages to the reader and a great impact and are well acknowledged. With different type of audience in mind, both have delivered their voice well in an amusing different way.

7 Limitations

Limited word count: due to the limitation of words, only limited concepts and themes could fit in, also, a wide number of interpretations were left out due to their depth and their need for a larger word count to be explained well.

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

8 References

Ende, M. (2009). Momo. National Geographic Books. <https://www.indigo.ca/en-ca/momo/9780140317534.html>

Orwell, G. (2017). Nineteen eighty-four. Mariner Books. <https://www.amazon.com/1984-George-Orwell/dp/1328869334>

Enteen, G. M. (1984). GEORGE ORWELL AND THE THEORY OF TOTALITARIANISM: A 1984 RETROSPECTIVE. *The Journal of General Education*, 36(3), 206–215. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/27797000>

Atkins, J. (1984). Orwell in 1984. *College Literature*, 11(1), 34–43. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25111577>

Hole, R. (2007). Nineteen eighty-four's dystopian vision: power and the individual. Agder University College. [Nineteen eighty-four's dystopian vision: power and the individual - CORE](#)

Goodhew, L., & Loy, D. R. (2002). Momo, Dogen, and the commodification of time. *KronoScope*, 2(1), 97–107. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15685240260186817>

Roback, J. (1985). The Economic Thought of George Orwell. *The American Economic Review*, 75(2), 127–132. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1805583>

Peck, R. N. (1991). MOMO, A RAGGED LITTLE GIRL, SHOWS THE WAY TO UTOPIA: A STUDY OF LISTENING, IMAGINING, AND TAKING TIME IN A RECENT GERMAN NOVEL. *Utopian Studies*, 3, 79–85. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20718928>

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

Sockfood. (2022, March 30). How Momo is Anti-Capitalist - Sockfood1 - medium. *Medium*.
<https://medium.com/@sockfood1/how-momo-is-anti-capitalist-8593df666981>

Polster, H. (2016). Corrupting capitalism: Michael Ende's Momo and "Cathedral Station." *Studies in 20th & 21st Century Literature*, 40(2). <https://doi.org/10.4148/2334-4415.1886>

Suckert, L. (2021). The coronavirus and the temporal order of capitalism: Sociological observations and the wisdom of a children's book. *The Sociological Review*, 69(6), 1162-1178.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/00380261211024890>

Dr Aidan. (2022, November 27). *1984: "Doublethink" explained* [Video]. YouTube.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QEhRUY4yAIg>

Cánovas, C. P., & Teuscher, U. (2012). Much more than money. *Pragmatics & Cognition*, 20(3), 546–569. <https://doi.org/10.1075/pc.20.3.05pag>

Gleason, A. (1984). "Totalitarianism" in 1984. *The Russian Review*, 43(2), 145–159.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/129750>

Nikolajeva, M. (2009). Time and Totalitarianism. *Journal of the Fantastic in the Arts*, 20(2 (76)), 184–192. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24352243>

Blakemore, S. (1984). Language and Ideology in Orwell's 1984. *Social Theory and Practice*, 10(3), 349–356. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23556571>

A comparison between Momo and 1984 as social fiction novels

Baykent, U. Ö. (2023). Totalitarianism and individualism unveiled: Hobbes and Orwell. *Kaygı. Bursa Uludağ Üniversitesi Fen-edebiyat Fakültesi Felsefe Dergisi* : <https://doi.org/10.20981/kaygi.1348193>

Crochet, J. W. (2023, August 24). “Orwell’s ‘1984’ Totalitarian Media Manipulation and Control: Lessons for Business Leadership Today.” <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/orwells-1984-totalitarian-media-manipulation-control-lessons-crochet>

Simurdić, I. M. (2020). An Unlikely hero: Reconsidering Michael Ende’s Momo as a divine child. *Filolog*, 22(22), 262–282. <https://doi.org/10.21618/fil2022262s>

Prezi, J. D. O. (n.d.). *Marxism in 1984*. prezi.com. <https://prezi.com/lz8trnxxbv09/marxism-in-1984/>

The Oxford Dictionary of Philosophy. (2008). In Oxford University Press eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acref/9780199541430.001.0001>

Symons, J. (1949). “Times Literary Supplement,” in (ed) Meyers, J. (1975). *George Orwell the Critical Heritage*. London; Routledge Boston: Routledge & K. Paul. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203196359>